

Objectives	Outcome measures
Primary objectives	
To determine if primary RSV-A challenge increases the risk of secondary Spn6B carriage using classical culture	Colonisation rates of Spn6B determined by classical culture
Secondary objectives	
To confirm co-infection model safety for participants	Absence of SAEs/AESIs relating to inoculation throughout the study
To determine if primary RSV-A challenge increases the risk of secondary Spn6B carriage using molecular methods	Colonisation rates of Spn6B determined by RT-qPCR
To determine if primary RSV-A infection increases the risk of secondary Spn6B carriage	Colonisation rates of Spn6B determined by classical culture and molecular methods
To determine if primary RSV-A challenge or infection alters the density of secondary Spn6B carriage	Density of Spn6B carriage by classical culture and molecular methods
To determine if primary RSV-A challenge or infection alters the duration of secondary Spn6B carriage	Quantification of Spn6B determined longitudinally by classical culture and RT-qPCR
To determine if primary Spn6B challenge alters the risk of secondary RSV-A infection	RSV-A attack rates determined by RT-qPCR
To determine if primary Spn6B carriage alters the risk of secondary RSV-A infection	RSV-A attack rates determined by RT-qPCR
To determine if primary Spn6B challenge or carriage alters the viral load of secondary RSV-A infection (AUC of density over time)	RSV-A viral load determined by RT-qPCR
To determine if primary Spn6B challenge or carriage alters the duration of secondary RSV-A infection	Duration of RSV-A detection and quantification determined by RT-qPCR
To determine if co-infection with RSV-A and Spn6B alter URTI and LRTI symptoms	Number of URTI and LRTI symptoms per participant after secondary challenge
Longitudinal assessment of viral and bacterial shedding from the nose in both arms of the study	Shedding of pathogens from the nose and throat will be assessed by coughing plate, hand swab after nose touching and facemasks assessments RSV-A viral load and Spn6B density by RT-qPCR

To determine if primary Spn6B carriage increases the proportion of participants from whom live RSV-A can be isolated from their hands	Shedding of pathogens from the nose and throat will be assessed by coughing plate, hand swab after nose touching and facemasks assessments
To determine if primary or secondary RSV-A infection increases the proportion of participants from whom live Spn6B can be isolated from their hands	Shedding of pathogens from the nose and throat will be assessed by coughing plate, hand swab after nose touching and facemasks assessments
To determine if Spn6B carriage density correlates with bacterial shedding	Shedding of pathogens from the nose and throat will be assessed by coughing plate, hand swab after nose touching and facemasks assessments
To determine if RSV-A nasal and throat viral load correlates with viral shedding	Shedding of pathogens from the nose and throat will be assessed by coughing plate, hand swab after nose touching and facemasks assessments
To determine if the outpatient RSV-A challenge model is associated with any increased risk of infection in household contacts	Nasopharyngeal or nasal swabs of household contacts for two weeks following RSV-A challenge visit
Exploratory objectives	
To identify if primary Spn6B carriage alters immune responses to secondary RSV-A infection (innate and adaptive)	Assessment of immune responses including nasal cytokines and cell populations as well as RSV-specific antibodies and cellular immunity before and after each pathogen challenge
To identify how primary RSV-A challenge or infection alters immune responses to secondary Spn6B carriage	Assessment of immune responses including nasal cytokines and cell populations as well as Spn6B-specific antibodies and cellular immunity before and after each pathogen challenge
Nasal cells gene expression alterations and their visualization (spatial location) within nasal tissue	Longitudinal analysis of the spatial microenvironment and transcriptomics of nasal tissue samples
Characterize transcriptional changes in immune cells (via single cell and bulk RNA sequencing) in response to RSV-A and Spn6B challenge/infection/carriage.	RNAseq analysis to determine gene induction and regulation to identify gene signatures (cell specific where possible) that correlate with susceptibility to infection, as well as alterations in immune responses and symptoms during co-infection
Assess pneumococcal transcriptional alterations in response to RSV-A co-infection	Determination of gene induction and regulation to identify bacterial response to viral co-infection

Primary, secondary, and exploratory objectives and outcomes of the RESPECCT study. RSV-A: Respiratory Syncytial Virus-A; Spn6B; Streptococcus pneumoniae serotype 6B; AE; adverse event; AESI; adverse event of special interest; SAE: significant adverse event; RT-qPCR: reverse transcription quantitative polymerase chain reaction; URTI: upper respiratory tract infection; LRTI: lower respiratory tract infection; RNAseq: RNA sequencing.